

Effects of Single Non-transferrable Vote (SNTV) Systems on Tribal Representation: Preliminary Findings from Jordan and Kuwait

Courtney Freer

*Courtney Freer is a Visiting Assistant Professor of Middle Eastern Studies at Emory University. She is the author of *Rentier Islamism: The Role of the Muslim Brotherhood in Gulf Monarchies* (Oxford University Press, 2018) and *The Resilience of Parliamentary Politics in Kuwait: Rentierism, Ideology, and Mobilization* (Oxford University Press, 2024). Email: courtney.jean.freer@emory.edu*

The single non-transferrable vote (SNTV) system, sometimes called “one person one vote” does just that: it grants each voter only one vote, rather than allowing each person to cast votes for multiple candidates. This system, though straightforward and easy to understand, is rarely implemented, largely due to the tendency of such a system to disadvantage organized political blocs (Butto and Kim 2012, Gao and Templeman 2023). Nonetheless, it was used in Jordan between 1993 and 2016 and has been in place in Kuwait since 2012. Both countries, notably, house large, politically active tribal blocs that have been forced to navigate changes to electoral systems and processes. This piece is a first step to explain the effects of the SNTV system in each case and the reasons that and extent to which its effects have varied in both states in its ability to regulate representation of tribal blocs. As to Kuwait, Andrew Leber and I have noted elsewhere that the overall representation of tribes has not shifted meaningfully with the introduction of the new system (Freer and Leber 2021). In Jordan, findings are a bit more complicated: tribes on a whole seem not to have been disadvantaged by the system, solely those antagonistic to the regime. This piece therefore examines the efficacy of SNTV systems in influencing

tribal votes in two hybrid regimes in which such systems have been put in place. Overall, SNTV appears to have been largely ineffective in reducing the so-called tribal vote in Kuwait and has solely been partially successful in so doing in Jordan.

The Management of Tribes in Hybrid Regimes

Jordan and Kuwait qualify as hybrid regimes, states with strong monarchies which also host meaningful parliamentary elections (Brown 2012, 17-18). As such, the laws governing their elections have been the subject of extensive study, largely to determine whether elections under authoritarianism or semi-authoritarianism are ideologically and politically meaningful (Freer 2018), merely a tool for the disbursement of patronage (Lust 2009, 122-135), or a means of appearing to support democratic outcomes without effectively doing so (Brown 2012, 7-8).

The implementation of the SNTV system is often portrayed in this literature (Case 2006) as one means by which monarchies can control electoral outcomes. When each voter is limited to selecting a single candidate, coordination issues arise, primarily for organized political groups. As Gao and Templeman

conclude, “SNTV creates several problems for organized political groups such as parties or, in the Jordanian case, tribes seeking to maximize the number of seats they win” (Gao and Templeman 2023).

In Jordan and Kuwait, the implementation of SNTV has been met with concern from both ideologically and tribally organized political blocs. Many who oppose the system consider it a means of centralizing political control in the hands of ruling families at the expense of tribal figures and Islamists in particular, as these are often the most organized political blocs. Then-leader of the Jordanian Muslim Brotherhood affiliate Islamic Action Front (IAF) Hamza Mansour claimed, when SNTV was put in place, that the system “forfeits the will of Jordanian citizens” (Köprülü 2014). In Jordan, the political opposition made these very complaints about the system in 2012, having made them decades earlier, with some parties boycotting the 2010 election held under the system, on charges that it is skewed to benefit tribes and particularly East Banker tribes (Köprülü 2014). In Kuwait, the amir’s announcement that voters would receive one, rather than the previous four, votes in 2012, led to an opposition-wide boycott that lasted between 2012 and 2016. There is still considerable resistance to this electoral system, which has also led political blocs to put in place new strategies in elections (Tavana 2018).

Jordan and Kuwait are, of course, quite different states, and the goal of comparing them is not to lessen or ignore the distinctiveness of each country. Jordan houses a large Palestinian population and allows for the legal organization of political parties, although parties remain weak and since 1992 have been required to register with the Ministry of Interior. Kuwait, on the other hand, has a majority

expatriate population, none of whom has the right to vote, and does not house official political parties, although political blocs fulfill many of the same responsibilities of parties in other countries. In both states, which have substantial populations who identify politically and socially with tribal affiliations, discourse has emerged about concerns that the political system could become “tribalized” (Al-Jabri 2018).

The Jordanian Case

SNTV was introduced to Jordan in 1993, abolishing a previously applied multiple vote system. Russell Lucas explains, “The new electoral system benefited regime supporters—especially those with tribal support. The change in the Election Law would make the regime’s life easier” (Köprülü 2014). In 2012, the system was altered such that SNTV was put in place in 60 percent of districts, the remainder of which were organized under single member plurality districts (SMD) through a first past the post system (Kao 2022).

Kao has found that, in SNTV districts, tribal representatives won seats largely due to support from fellow tribal members, whereas under SMD, electoral coalitions emerged across tribal lines (Kao 2022). In short, when both systems existed side by side, “under SNTV rules, strategic voting for a consensus candidate diminishes while sincere voting on the basis of social identity increases” (Kao 2022, 1245). SNTV, rather than diminishing the relevance of tribal groups at the polls, therefore appears in danger of reifying it.

The Kuwaiti Case

Kuwait houses a unicameral parliament with 50 elected seats; appointed cabinet members automatically become members of parliament

as well. As noted above, in 2012, Amir Shaykh Sabah introduced a system of SNTV, altering the previous arrangement in which each Kuwaiti voter had four votes. Implementation of the new system prompted an electoral boycott and therefore initially affected the composition of but not the overall proportion of tribal MPs in Kuwaiti parliament.

Notably, most of Kuwait's tribes have increasingly switched from "service MPs" to members of the opposition—particularly since driving forward the Karamat Watan protests in 2012 (Albloshi 2018). In addition, since the imposition of a five-district system in 2006, which was intended to reduce opportunities for gerrymandering, most tribal constituents have been located in outlying districts IV and V, leading tribes to be *over-represented* in those areas but *under-represented* by the system overall. Andrew Leber and I found, in examining elections between 1991 and 2020, that "Tribes may be overrepresented by the number of winning candidates, but their votes are underrepresented by district size (i.e., tribe-heavy districts have more voters per parliamentary representative). If anything, therefore, tribes have been under-represented in the National Assembly" (Freer and Leber 2021, 20-21).

In the first election held after the imposition of the SNTV system, smaller tribes gained seats over larger tribes, in part due to some larger tribes contemplating a boycott, but larger tribes have since that time recovered their position. Indeed, the 2020 legislature saw the largest number of tribe-affiliated MPs (29 out of 50) since 1992 (Freer and Leber 2021). In fact, the tribal vote today, then, still appears to account for about 20 of 50 seats in parliament, and so SNTV has largely failed to contain it.

Conclusions

Many segments of nontribal populations in Kuwait and Jordan charge that tribal groups serve as harmful conduits of patronage, rather than as meaningful political actors. These claims should be interrogated more thoroughly in these cases and others to understand the extent to which identity politics are necessarily linked to clientelism. In the Kuwaiti case, the era of "service MPs" remains, although some tribal figures have also become members of the political opposition (Albloshi 2018; Freer and Leber 2021, 26-27). If areas of contact on political issues can be found between tribal and non-tribal groups, coordination across tribal / non-tribal lines could facilitate political learning about how best to circumvent challenges presented by electoral systems implemented by hybrid regimes.

In Jordan, Kao charges that the system "resulted in an electorate fractured along tribal lines and in-group favoritism among elected representatives" (Kao 2022, 1245). The system may in fact reify tribal distinctions, which in turn makes it more difficult for these groups to coordinate with non-tribal segments of the political opposition, but it also makes integration of the population politically more difficult.

This short piece represents only a first step in examining the actual versus intended effects of the implementation of SNTV systems. More work should be done on the effect of district size and arrangement influences tribal representation in parliaments of hybrid regime states. ♦

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